

A Review of Spatial and Temporal Analysis Models: GTWR, STARIMA and STARDL

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January 17, 2022

Summary

GTWR, STARIMA, and STARDL are three spatial-temporal analysis approaches that are expansions of their respective basic models. Deciding which approach is most appropriate in a given research context can be difficult, so this paper reviews the approaches in detail. The GTWR model produces superior results when compared to temporally weighted (i.e. lagged) regression models, while the STARIMA model delivers better performance than the ARIMA model. As for the STARDL model, there are still many aspects that could be investigated and expanded.

KEYWORDS: Spatial Temporal Analysis, GTWR, STARIMA, STARDL

1. Introduction

Many dynamic phenomena change over both by space and time. To understand interactions in space and time it is important to model how (spatio-temporal *patterns*) and why (spatio-temporal *processes*) things change. Understanding spatio-temporal process and their historical patterns is essential for making predictions about the future. However, analysing spatial and temporal data and quantifying spatio-temporal patterns and processes is challenging as space is commonly captured in two-dimensions (through longitude and latitude) and time data in only one (Rowe and Arribas-Bel, 2021).

This research will compare different methods for understanding spatio-temporal data in order to support spatio-temporal inference and process understanding. Here GTWR (Geographical and Temporal Weighted Regression), STARIMA (Spatiotemporal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average), and STARDL (Spatio-Temporal AutoRegressive Distributed Lag) methods for spatial and temporal analysis will be reviewed. These models are extensions of basic models commonly employed in statistical analyses.

The GTWR model is an extension of Geographically Weighted Regression (GWR), an approach for modelling process spatial heterogeneity processes. It allows for variation in the relationships between a response and a set of covariates across geographic space (Charlton and Fotheringham, 2009). Huang et al., (2010) extended GWR into the temporal dimension by weighting matrices in order to incorporate temporal effects into GWR. Other researchers then used this model to conduct the spatial-temporal analysis in a variety of cases.

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The STARIMA model was first introduced by Cliff and Ord (1975). They added spatial dimensions into the AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) model, which is a time series data model by Box and Jenkins (1970). The STARIMA model is described by Pfeifer and Deutsch as a three-stage iterative model building procedure (identification, estimation, and diagnostic checking) (Pfeifer and Deutsch, 1980a, 1980b). Pfeifer and Deutsch described the STARMA identification consideration modeling for the first stage (Pfeifer and Deutsch, 1980c), compared the estimation procedures of the STAR model parameter for the second stage, and explained the computation procedure for testing hypotheses about G on the last stage (Phillip E Pfeifer and Deutsch, 1980d). It is completed with the application of the STARIMA model for forecasting in a business context using hotel data (Pfeifer and Bodily, 1990).

A third approach based on the ARDL (AutoRegressive Distributed Lag) model (Shin and Thornton 2018; Pesaran et al., 2001; Pesaran and Shin, 1998; Shin et al., 2014). This was extended to space and time through the STARDL model (Shin and Thornton, 2018) for handling spatially correlated data. The ARDL model combines an autoregressive component with a distributed lag to calculate dynamic parameters and explain how variables interact over time. The STARDL model is a system of ARDL equations, each of which is augmented with variables defined using spatially-weighted averages (Cho et al., 2020). The STARDL framework integrates multiple spatial models, and has been used with the spatial Durbin model (Lee and Yu, 2010 and Elhorst, 2014) as well as Aquaro, Bailey, and Pesaran's (2015) heterogeneous spatial autoregressive panel data model.

2. Methodology

2.1. GTWR

The most widely used GTWR model is from Huang et al., (2010). The following is the model:

$$y_1 = \beta_0(u_i, v_i, t_i) + \sum_k \beta_k(u_i, v_i, t_i)x_{ik} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where y_1 is the dependent variable at the observation point (u_i, v_i, t_i) which (u_i, v_i, t_i) represents the three dimensional coordinates; x_{ik} is the value of the k -th explanatory variable of the sample point i ; $\beta_k(u_i, v_i, t_i)$ represents the regression coefficient of the k -th variable of the observation point i ; and ε_i represents the independent random error term.

The estimation of $\beta_k(u_i, v_i, t_i)$ can be expressed using Weighted Least Square (WLS) as follows:

$$\hat{\beta}(u_i, v_i, t_i) = [X^T W(u_i, v_i, t_i) X]^{-1} X^T W(u_i, v_i, t_i) y \quad (2)$$

where $W(u_i, v_i, t_i) = \text{diag}(w_{i1}, w_{i2}, \dots, w_{in})$ is a weight matrix of the observation point i and n is the number of observations. w_{ij} is a space-time distance function whose diagonal elements $w_{ij} (1 \leq j \leq n)$ correspond to the weights when calibrating a weighted regression adjacent to observation point i . The most often used weighting function in the GTWR model is the Gaussian Kernel Function (Chen *et al.*, 2021), which is stated as follows:

$$w_{ij} = \exp\left(\frac{-(d_{ij}^{ST})^2}{h^2}\right) \quad (3)$$

where h is a bandwidth parameter and the spatial-temporal distance between observations i and j is measured by d_{ij}^{ST} . In the GTWR model, the spatial-temporal distance is described by a linear combination of spatial distance and temporal distance as follows:

$$d_{ij}^{ST} = \sqrt{\lambda [(u_i - u_j)^2 + (v_i - v_j)^2] + \mu (t_i - t_j)^2} \quad (4)$$

where λ and μ represent scale parameters to balance the spatial and temporal effects, respectively. If the observation data has no temporal data then $\mu = 0$ and the GTWR model is simplified to a GWR model. On the other hand, if only time nonstationarity and time distance are considered then $\lambda = 0$, and the GTWR model becomes to a TWR model.

2.2. STARIMA

The STARIMA model (Pfeifer and Deutsch, 1980c) is expressed as follows:

$$z(t) = - \sum_{k=1}^p \sum_{l=0}^{\lambda_k} \phi_{kl} W^{(t)} z(t-k) + \varepsilon(t) - \sum_{k=1}^q \sum_{l=0}^{m_k} \theta_{kl} W^{(t)} \varepsilon(t-k) \quad (5)$$

where p is the autoregressive order; q is the moving average order; λ^k is the spatial order of the k^{th} autoregressive term; m^k is the spatial order of the k^{th} moving average term; ϕ_{kl} is the autoregressive parameter at temporal lag k and spatial lag l ; θ_{kl} is the moving average parameter at temporal lag k and spatial lag l ; $W^{(t)}$ is the $N \times N$ matrix of weights for spatial order l ; and $\varepsilon(t)$ is the random normally distributed error vector at time t with,

$$E[\varepsilon(t)] = 0$$

$$E[\varepsilon(t)\varepsilon(t+s)'] = \begin{cases} G & s = 0 \\ 0 & s \neq 0 \end{cases}$$

$$E[z(t)\varepsilon(t+s)'] = 0 \quad \text{for } s > 0$$

This specific model is referred to as the STARIMA ($p_{\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_p}, q_{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_q}$) model. If there are only autoregressive terms then $q = 0$ and the model is called a STAR (Space-Time AutoRegressive) model. However, if there is no autoregressive terms then $p = 0$ and the model refers to STMA (Space-Time Moving Average) model.

2.3. STARDL

The STARDL (p, q) model (Shin and Thornton, 2018) is specified as follows:

$$y_{it} = \sum_{l=1}^p \phi_{il} y_{i,t-l} + \sum_{l=0}^p \phi_{il}^* y_{i,t-l}^* + \sum_{l=0}^q \pi_{il}' x_{i,t-l} + \sum_{l=0}^q \pi_{il}^* x_{i,t-l}^* + \alpha_i + u_{it} \quad (6)$$

for $i = 1, \dots, N$ and $t = 1, \dots, T$, where y_{it} is the scalar dependent variable of the i th spatial unit at time t , $x_{it} = (x_{it}^1, \dots, x_{it}^{1K})'$ is a $K \times 1$ vector of exogenous regressors with a $K \times 1$ vector of parameters, $\pi_0 = (\pi_0^1, \dots, \pi_0^K)'$. Similarly for $y_{i,t-l}$ and $x_{i,t-l}$. Spatial interactions between units, both contemporaneously and with lags, are captured via the spatial variables, y_{it}^* and x_{it}^* , defined by:

$$y_{it}^* = \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} y_{jt} = w_i y_t; \quad \text{with } \mathbf{y}_{N \times 1} = (y_{1t}, \dots, y_{Nt})' \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{it}^* = (x_{it}^{1*}, \dots, x_{it}^{K*})' \equiv \left(\sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} x_{jt}^1, \dots, \sum_{j=1}^N w_{ij} x_{jt}^K \right)' = (w_i \otimes I_K) x_t; \quad \mathbf{x}_t = \begin{pmatrix} x_{1t} \\ \dots \\ x_{Nt} \end{pmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where $w_i = (w_{i1}, \dots, w_{iN})$ denotes a $1 \times N$ vector of (non-stochastic) spatial weights determined a priori with $w_{ii} = 0$.

The STARDL (p, q) specification in (6) reveals some information (Shin and Thornton, 2018). If ϕ_{it} 's and π_{it} 's are statistically significant, this points to the usual temporal dynamics (The ARDL model). In addition, if ϕ_{it}^* 's (the endogenous effect) and π_{it}^* 's (the contextual effect) are statistically significant, this indicates an importance of spatial dependence as well as spatio-temporal or diffusion dynamics.

3. Discussion

GTWR has generally been shown to out-perform temporally weighted (i.e. lagged) regression models (Chen *et al.*, 2021; Li and Wang, 2020; Ma *et al.*, 2018; Sholihin *et al.*, 2017) although not always (Wei *et al.* 2019) if there are insufficient geographical locations. Some modifications have been proposed. Sholihin *et al.* (2017) recommended a different kernel functions and Que *et al.* (2020) noted that time was poorly handled in several GTWR models and proposed STWR (Spatiotemporal Weighted Regression) which outperformed GTWR.

STARIMA models are widely used in a number of case studies. A comparative analyses have shown that the STARIMA model outperforms the ARIMA model (Awwad *et al.*, 2021; Ding *et al.*, 2011; Guan *et al.*, 2017) but not always (Freire, 2019). Rentzelos (2019) identified the need for spatiotemporal resolutions sensitivity to be considered in such analyses.

Little research has used the STARDL model. Ardiansyah *et al.* (2021) and Cook *et al.* (2021) conducted similar research aiming to combine spatial temporal dimensions into the ARDL model, using different case studies. Shin and Thornton (2018) valued Iraqi war casualties and showed that it was able to capture spatiotemporal contaminations affecting the impact of insurgent deaths on civilian mortality.

4. Conclusion and Further Work

The three methods succeeded in integrating spatial and temporal effects into a single model. The GTWR and STARIMA models show much better performance than the previous basic methods. The STARDL method has many areas that requiring further research and development. Future work will compare and assess the performance of the three methodologies using describing the spatial-temporal properties of tourism and travel patterns from social media data.

5. Acknowledgements

This study is supported by the Indonesian Endowment Fund for Education/Lembaga Pengelola Dana Pendidikan (LPDP).

References

- Aquaro, M., Bailey, N. and Pesaran, M.H. (2015), "Quasi Maximum Likelihood Estimation of Spatial Models with Heterogeneous Coefficients", *USC-INET Research Paper*.
- Ardiansyah, M., Djuraidah, A., Sumertajaya, I.M., Wigena, A.H. and Fitrianto, A. (2021), "Development of the Panel ARDL by Adding Space-Time effect to Modeling Monthly Paddy Producer Price in Java", *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, Vol. 1863.
- Awwad, F.A., Mohamoud, M.A. and Abonazel, M.R. (2021), "Estimating COVID-19 Cases in Makkah region of Saudi Arabia: Space-time ARIMA modeling", *PLoS ONE*, Public Library of Science, Vol. 16 No. 4 April.
- Charlton, M. and Fotheringham, S. (2009), "GEOGRAPHICALLY WEIGHTED REGRESSION WHITE PAPER", Ireland.
- Chen, Y., Chen, M., Huang, B., Wu, C. and Shi, W. (2021), "Modeling the Spatiotemporal Association Between COVID-19 Transmission and Population Mobility Using Geographically and

- Temporally Weighted Regression”, *GeoHealth*, John Wiley and Sons Inc, Vol. 5 No. 5.
- Cho, J.S., Greenwood-Nimmo, M. and Shin, Y. (2020), *Recent Developments of the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Modelling Framework* *, *Journal of Economic Surveys*, p. joes.12450.
- Cliff, A.D. and Ord, J.K. (1975), “Space-Time Modelling with an Application to Regional Forecasting”, *Transactions of the Institute of British Geographers*, Vol. 64, pp. 119–128.
- Cook, S.J., Hays, J.C. and Franzese, R.J. (2021), “STADL Up! The Spatio-Temporal Autoregressive Distributed Lag Model for TSCS Data Analysis”.
- Ding, Q., Wang, X., Zhang, X. and Sun, Z. (2011), “Forecasting Traffic Volume with Space-Time ARIMA Model”, *Advanced Materials Research*, Vol. 156–157, Trans Tech Publications Ltd, pp. 979–983.
- Elhorst, J.P. (2014), “SPRINGER BRIEFS IN REGIONAL SCIENCE : Spatial Econometrics From Cross-Sectional Data to Spatial Panels”, Springer.
- Freire, S. (2019), “Space Time ARMA Models and Their Application to Radioactivity in Portugal”.
- Guan, D., Huang, ; Lei and Qu, Q. (2017), “A Predicting Method of Urban Traffic Network Volume Based on STARIMA Model”, *CICTP 2017: Transportation Reform and Change—Equity, Inclusiveness, Sharing, and Innovation*.
- Huang, B., Wu, B. and Barry, M. (2010), “Geographically and Temporally Weighted Regression for Modeling Spatio-Temporal Variation in House Prices”, *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, Vol. 24 No. 3, pp. 383–401.
- Lee, L. fei and Yu, J. (2010), “Some Recent Developments in Spatial Panel Data Models”, *Regional Science and Urban Economics*, Vol. 40 No. 5, pp. 255–271.
- Li, M. and Wang, J. (2020), “Spatial-Temporal Distribution Characteristics and Driving Mechanism of Green Total Factor Productivity in China’s Logistics Industry”, *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*, HARD Publishing Company, Vol. 30 No. 1, pp. 201–213.
- Ma, X., Zhang, J., Ding, C. and Wang, Y. (2018), “A Geographically and Temporally Weighted Regression Model to Explore The Spatiotemporal Influence of Built Environment on Transit Ridership”, *Computers, Environment and Urban Systems*, Elsevier Ltd, Vol. 70, pp. 113–124.
- Pesaran, M.H., Shin, Y. and Smith, R.J. (2001), “Bounds Testing Approaches to The Analysis of Level Relationships”, *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, Vol. 16 No. 3, pp. 289–326.
- Pfeifer, P.E. and Bodily, S.E. (1990), “A test of space-time arma modelling and forecasting of hotel data”, *Journal of Forecasting*, Vol. 9, pp. 255–272.
- Pfeifer, P.E. and Deutsch, S.J. (1980a), “A Three-Stage Iterative Procedure for Space-Time Modeling”, *Technometrics* , Vol. 22, pp. 35–47.
- Pfeifer, P.E. and Deutsch, S.J. (1980b), “A STARIMA Model-Building Procedure with Application to Description and Regional Forecasting”, *Geographers*, Vol. 5, pp. 330–349.
- Pfeifer, P.E. and Deutsch, S.J. (1980c), “Identification and Interpretation of First Order Space-Time ARMA Models”, *Technometrics* , Vol. 22, pp. 397–408.
- Pfeifer, P.E. and Deutsch, S.J. (1980d), “Independence and Sphericity Tests for the Residuals of Space-Time Arma Models”, *Communications in Statistics - Simulation and Computation*, Vol. 9 No. 5, pp. 533–549.
- Que, X., Ma, X., Ma, C. and Chen, Q. (2020), “A Spatiotemporal Weighted Regression Model (STWRv1.0) for Analyzing Local Non-stationarity in Space and Time”, *Geoscientific Model Development Discussions*, pp. 1–33.
- Rentzelos, A. (2019), “Exploring a Space-Time Autoregressive Moving Average (STARMA) Model in Spatial Crime Forecasting”.
- Rowe, F. and Arribas-Bel, D. (2021), “Spatial Modelling for Data Scientists”, Liverpool.
- Shin, Y. and Thornton, M. (2018), “The Spatio-Temporal Autoregressive Distributed Lag Modelling Approach to an Analysis of the Spatial Heterogeneity and Diffusion Dependence *”.
- Shin, Y., Yu, B. and Greenwood-Nimmo, M. (2014), “Modelling Asymmetric Cointegration and Dynamic Multipliers in a Nonlinear ARDL Framework”, edited by Sickles, R.C. and Horrace, W.C. *Festschrift in Honor of Peter Schmidt*, Springer, New York, pp. 281–314.
- Sholihin, M., Soleh, A.M. and Djuraidah, A. (2017), “Geographically and Temporally Weighted Regression (GTWR) for Modeling Economic Growth using R”, *IJCSN-International Journal of Computer Science and Network*, Vol. 6 No. 6.
- Wei, Q., Zhang, L., Duan, W. and Zhen, Z. (2019), “Global and Geographically and Temporally

Weighted Regression Models for Modeling PM2.5 in Heilongjiang, China from 2015 to 2018”, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, MDPI AG, Vol. 16 No. 24.

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